

New Findings About Atmospheric Electricity Build-up and Dissipation

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Abstract— Water plays a major role in generating atmospheric electricity, which, in many cases, can be understood by considering the role of water in matter electrification. A new picture of electrostatic phenomena emerged during the past twenty years, following the discovery of charge mosaics in insulators and the atmospheric water vapor's ability to exchange charge with solids and liquids. Related findings are the unique position of water in the triboelectric series and charge separation during phase transitions of water. These and other intriguing effects are now explained by water ion partition at interfaces. The new picture of matter electrification includes the Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars effect on interfacial electrification and the various processes that manifest this effect. Still, the discovery of chemical reactions in the electrified interfaces of insulators revealed a connection between chemical and electrostatic phenomena that creates new perspectives for radical change in energy and chemical production. Moreover, this new knowledge contributes plausible explanations for hitherto challenging atmospheric electrical phenomena, including a mechanism for high voltage production in clouds.

Keywords— self-electrification, interfaces, contact charging, Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars effect, “on-water” reactions

I. INTRODUCTION

Surprising water-based processes have been revealed in the literature in the past twenty years [1] under various keywords: “on-water” chemistry [2], droplet microreactors [3], hydrovoltaics [4], hygroelectricity [5], electro-crystallization, electrowetting, condensation, and adhesion. These findings challenge established experimental practice and were not predicted by theoretical or computational approaches, thus requiring new ideas for their interpretation.

The chemical knowledge expressed in textbooks and the current literature largely refers to electroneutral single molecules and bulk matter. The electrified interfaces found everywhere are specialized topics treated in colloid and surface science, catalysis, and electrochemistry, but they are neglected in other disciplines. This situation is consistent with the assumption that macroscopic matter is typically electroneutral, often stated as the Principle of

Electroneutrality, which “expresses the fact that all pure substances carry a net charge of zero” [6].

The essential idea was proposed by L. Pauling in 1948 and revised in 1970: “Stable molecules and crystals have electronic structures such that the electric charge of each atom is close to zero. Close to zero means between -1 and +1” [7]. A pure substance is challenging to find in the real world, and Pauling's electroneutrality is not strictly neutral. On the other hand, new explanations for challenging experimental results if this concept is overlooked [8].

This work presents novel statements supported by recent experimental results or theoretical arguments relevant to the problems of atmospheric electricity. These statements oppose incorrect but widespread and persistent beliefs showing new approaches to solve persistent problems.

II. NEW RESULTS AND IDEAS ON MATTER ELECTRIFICATION

The ideas are presented in subsections whose titles are statements supported by recent experimental results. Each subsection describes the evidence supporting the statement and its implications for atmospheric phenomena.

A. Matter is usually electrified.

The Earth surface and the atmosphere are parts of the capacitor. Beyond, matter usually forms polyphasic systems. Thus, any material system on Earth is a charge mosaic since interfaces are always expected to acquire excess charge, following the Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars effect. This is due to the inevitable differences in the permittivity and electrical conductivity of adjacent phases. Higher permittivity allows for larger charge excess in a phase due to the lowered electrostatic repulsion between charge carriers [9].

On the other hand, higher conductivity implies faster charge transfer within a phase. In an interface normal to the electric field, charge accumulation is expected for the following reasons: in the more conductive phase, positive charge carriers move towards the interface, but the negative carriers move away. However, the accumulated charge cannot migrate fast in

the adjacent low-conductivity phase. Thus, the interface acquires an excess positive charge.

B. Electrostatic phenomena are observed under high relative humidity.

Instructions for laboratory experiments usually include a low-humidity environment, where contact charging between two different materials is often pronounced, causing curious observations but also harmful electrostatic discharge. Thus, many people believe that electrostatic charge does not accumulate on any surfaces in humid environments because of charge conduction by adsorbed water that coats any surface except under dry conditions. However, the association between lightning and thunderstorm clouds is also familiar to any person, showing powerful electrification under wet conditions.

Recent research produced evidence of solid [10] and liquid [11] charging under high relative humidity. The most direct evidence comes from completely independent experiments on various systems: hygroelectricity and the related moisture-enabled charging of solids, delivering electric current; aqueous aerosol charging [12], detected directly by electrophoresis; direct Kelvin force microscopy (KFM) determination of charge on the surface of insulators, showing electric pattern change with atmospheric humidity.

In fact, preliminary experiments in our lab demonstrated intrinsic electrostatic charging in aerosols from various liquids [12]. Using a commercial compressed-air nebulizer, we generated a consistent aerosol current. Charge separation was detected by directing the aerosol into a Faraday cup and measuring the nebulizer's electrostatic potential with a Kelvin electrode, as seen in Fig. 1. The nebulizer, producing mist from deionized water or NaCl solutions, was cleaned with detergent, rinsed, immersed in ethanol, and dried to suppress residual charges. It was then filled using a syringe pump with a grounded needle [12].

Fig. 1 Setup for Measuring Charge on Aerosol: The electrostatic charge of the liquid and its reservoir is measured using a Kelvin probe, while the charge of the released aerosol is measured simultaneously with a Faraday cup [12, 13].

Using the setup described in Fig. 1, the electrostatic potential of the nebulizer and the aerosol charge were recorded. Figure 2 presents data for aerosols from deionized water and 1 mmol L⁻¹ sodium chloride solution. Initially, the nebulizer's electrostatic potential is < 3 V, and the detected charge in the Faraday cup is < 10⁻¹¹ C. When the compressor is activated for 30 seconds, both charge and potential are detected. Nebulizing deionized water results in a positively charged aerosol and a negatively charged nebulizer, while NaCl solution produces a negatively charged aerosol and a positively charged nebulizer. After the gas flow stops, no further charge accumulation is detected in the Faraday cup. The nebulizer with water shows a potential decay from -2500 to -500 V in five minutes, whereas the nebulizer with NaCl solution stabilizes at around +1600 V.

Fig. 2 The electrostatic potential of the nebulizer and the charge in the Faraday cup were measured over time as the nebulizer produced aerosol directed into the Faraday cup. (a) Aerosol from deionized water exhibited a positive charge, while the residual water in the nebulizer was negative. (b) Aerosol from sodium chloride solution displayed the opposite charging behavior [13].

C. The large electric polarization of water is a consequence of water ion partition and the realignment of its large molecular dipoles within a field.

Debye used dipolar molecule orientation with the applied field to determine dipole moments, an essential step in studying molecular structure [14]. Debye noted that this worked when the dipolar molecules were in the gas phase or a dilute solution in non-polar liquids. He also found that the measurements of dielectric constants and electric polarization of pure dipolar liquids could not be interpreted in the same

way due to the unknown hydrogen bonds that transform liquid water into a complex dynamic network, departing from the simple idea of the liquid as a disordered cluster of disconnected quasi-spherical molecules.

Explanations of the attraction of water drops or thin streams by an electrified object are often found in the literature, including electronic materials, which mention water molecule alignment as the sole source of large electric polarization. This is not consistent with Debye's findings, although this idea is implicit in his writings. Direct evidence opposing it comes from the experimental results obtained from electric impedance spectroscopy that were motivated by the development of radio technology, in the early 20th century. That led to the Maxwell-Wagner-Sillars effect mentioned in subsection A.

This knowledge was virtually ignored until the 1980s when literature citations became more frequent. The authors could not detect any mention of this effect in textbooks used by undergraduate students. Thus, current students still learn that water polarization is only due to water molecule reorientation, ignoring hundreds of papers showing results and proposals on water structure and dynamics and the position of water in the triboelectric series [15].

D. The change in the Gibbs energy calculated from standard thermodynamic tables shows whether a chemical reaction occurs spontaneously and to what extent in an ideal electroneutral system. However, since the matter is usually electrified, these results are modified to different extents in the real system charge mosaics.

Gibbs energy calculations have an enormous predictive power supported by experimental results. However, the widely used data for the thermodynamic properties of chemicals usually refer to electroneutral substances, not including surface factors and non-zero electric potential on the substances. It is explicit in the following statement by George Whitesides: Under non-zero conditions, the chemical potentials used in Gibbs energy calculations should be replaced by electrochemical potentials including an electrostatic term:

$$\mu_i = \mu_i^0 + RT \ln a_i + z_i FV \quad (1)$$

where μ_i^0 is the electrochemical potential under standard conditions, a_i is the activity of ion i , z_i is its charge, F is Faraday electrochemical equivalent and V is the local potential. Negative zFV contributions stabilize a chemical in a domain having opposite charges, but positive zFV increases its tendency to react chemically, changing well-known reactivity patterns.

This is explicitly recognized in some scientific fields, such as colloid and surface chemistry, electrochemistry and biochemistry and biophysics, and electrophysiology. The applications occur in many important products and technologies currently used on a large scale: powder coatings, electrophoretic separations, electrocrystallization, electrospinning, electrowetting, and electrosprays.

E. The chemical properties of a substance cannot be obtained using only the molecular energy states given by quantum-mechanical calculations combined with the Boltzmann distribution.

Theoretical chemistry employs quantum theory and statistical physics to calculate the energy states of molecules. Its methods promise to deliver every molecular property, including its reactivity, thermodynamic data, and activation energies of chemical reactions. It should thus largely supersede experimental methods of chemical investigation. However, this did not yet happen, for many decades after the publication of landmark books, although many partial successes were achieved. The difficulty has been largely assigned to computational problems, and quantum computing is now seen as a new possibility to have theoretical methods with strong predictive power.

Still, theoretical methods consider neutral or charged species under electroneutral environments, that are not found on Earth and perhaps elsewhere. It is a conceptual problem to be solved, independent of computational power.

F. Aqueous interfaces modify chemical reactivity, yielding surprising results and suggesting hitherto neglected or undisclosed geochemical and atmospheric phenomena.

A strong example supporting this statement is the status of molecular hydrogen in the environment. Hydrogen is a minor atmospheric component not detected underground until the past decade. Accordingly, its physiological effects have not received the attention of human, animal, or plant health researchers and experts.

This situation changed for two reasons. First, hydrogen peroxide formation in water interfaces with the atmosphere [16] and solids was a big surprise when first published, but it has already been detected in many systems. More recently, the authors [17] and other researchers found that molecular hydrogen appears together with peroxide under different circumstances. The other surprise was the discovery of large underground reservoirs of molecular hydrogen, initially in Mali, in Africa. Reservoirs have since been discovered in many regions, and the estimated reserves amount to five trillion tons of hydrogen, representing a new source of hydrogen for energy and chemical production [18].

The interfacial systems producing hydrogen and its peroxide in the laboratories are often aqueous aerosols. Since atmospheric clouds are also made of aqueous aerosols, it seems reasonable that hydrogen and hydrogen peroxide are formed in thunderclouds, maybe contributing to explaining the explosive events detected during thunderstorms.

G Electric fields decrease or eliminate metastability in the condensation of atmospheric water vapor by lowering the activation energy of the phase change, mainly due to the high water surface tension that decreases in electrified interfaces. Still, there is evidence for a non-classical phase transition mechanism in electrified water.

Metastability plays a crucial role in understanding phase transitions in various systems. It describes a state that appears stable but is actually in a local energy minimum rather than a global one. This state can persist for an extended period until a small perturbation leads to a transition to a more stable phase. Metastability is prominent in numerous physical, chemical, and biological processes.

Metastable states are observed in numerous scenarios, such as supercooling, superheating, and supersaturation. The classical nucleation theory provides a framework for understanding how phase transitions occur from a metastable state. According to this theory, a new phase begins with the nucleation of small clusters (or nuclei) within the old one. For instance, when water vapor condenses into liquid droplets or when a liquid crystallizes into a solid.

Surface tension plays a critical role in nucleation. It is the force that acts at the surface of a liquid, minimizing its surface area. The interfacial tension of a nucleus in its original environment affects the energy barrier that must be overcome for the nucleus to grow, following Eq. 2:

$$R = N_s Z_j \exp \exp \left(- \frac{\Delta G^*}{kT} \right) \quad (2)$$

where N_s is the number density of nuclei, Z_j is the probability that a nucleus at the top of the energy barrier will grow further, forming a stable particle, and ΔG^* is the energy barrier to the formation of nuclei, given by Eq (3):

$$\Delta G^* = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \Delta g_v + 4 \pi r^2 \gamma \quad (3)$$

where ΔG^* is the summation of two terms dependent on the particle radius, r . The first is the bulk contribution to Gibbs' energy change, below 0 °C, for ice formation, which is <0. The second is the surface contribution that reaches large positive values per mol when r is in the nanometric size range.

High surface tension means a higher energy barrier, making it harder for nuclei to form and grow. Conversely, lower surface tension facilitates nucleation. This balance is crucial in determining whether the small nuclei formed within a metastable state grow or dissociate back to their condition in the initial phase. In the first case, metastability will persist, while in the second case, the phase transition will progress until the system reaches a stable state.

Decreasing the surface tension in aqueous interfaces is achieved by electrically charging the liquid when charges accumulate at the interface [19]. Beyond the cases consistent with the classical theory, there are also cases of non-classical phase transition kinetics [20], such as those involving spinodal decomposition [21]. These phenomena occur under specific conditions and lead to unique and often rapid changes in material properties.

Spinodal decomposition occurs spontaneously and uniformly throughout the material when quenched into the spinodal region. Small fluctuations in composition or density

grow exponentially without the need to overcome an energy barrier.

The spinodal region is defined by the spinodal line in a phase diagram. Inside this region, any fluctuation in composition will lower the system's free energy, making it energetically favorable for the material to separate into two distinct phases. The critical point on the phase diagram marks the boundary beyond which spinodal decomposition can occur.

Hence, spinodal decomposition proceeds by the rapid, simultaneous growth of fluctuations throughout the material, leading to the formation of interconnected structures rather than isolated nuclei. The kinetics of spinodal decomposition are described by the Cahn-Hilliard equation, which models the evolution of composition fluctuations over time.

Spinodal decomposition is important in a variety of materials and applications and is widely used to impart desired properties to metals, polymers, and glasses. However, it has not yet been detected in the gas phase.

Recent results on the behavior of supersaturated water vapor within an electric field show the formation of tenuous needle-shaped domains whose density quickly increases, resembling spinodal phase separation. However, given the low vapor concentrations, the needles do not form interconnected structures like solid materials.

Metastable conditions can lead to significant and sometimes catastrophic events. Supercooling can result in rapid ice formation, causing damage in natural and industrial settings. Superheating can lead to explosive boiling, posing risks in both everyday and industrial scenarios. Supersaturation can cause sudden precipitation of solids, clogging pipelines and damaging equipment. It is often observed as the super-freezing of beverages placed in a refrigerator when its temperature is not controlled properly.

One notable example of a disaster caused by metastable conditions is the catastrophic explosion of superheated water. In industrial processes, superheated water can explosively convert to steam, releasing vast amounts of energy and causing severe damage and potential loss of life.

Another example is the phenomenon of supersaturation in cloud formation, which can lead to heavy and sudden precipitation, resulting in flash floods and landslides.

Breaking water vapor supersaturation in the atmosphere produces huge interfacial areas under the local electric potential gradient. The ensuing electrification of the water-air interfaces produces large electric potentials. Laboratory measurements of the charge carried by electrified ice crystals allow electric potential calculation in the range conducive to lightning.

Summing up, metastability is a critical concept in understanding phase transitions. The classical theory of nucleation, the role of surface tension, and the potential for disasters caused by supercooled, superheated, and supersaturated states highlight the importance of this phenomenon. Understanding metastability is essential for both advancing scientific knowledge and mitigating risks associated with these potentially hazardous conditions.

H. The interfacial tensions of the crystal surfaces in the crystallization environments determine crystal habit. Thus, lowering interfacial tensions by electrification changes crystal habits.

Interfacial tensions play a pivotal role in determining the habits or shapes of crystals as they grow. A crystal habit refers to its external shape, that is influenced by the internal arrangement of atoms or molecules and the external conditions during growth. Interfacial tension, the force per unit length existing at the interface between two phases, affects the growth rates of different crystal faces, ultimately shaping the crystal.

Crystals grow by adding material to their surfaces. Different faces of a crystal have different interfacial tensions due to their atomic or molecular structure. Faces with lower interfacial tension grow faster than those with higher tension because the latter increases the system energy. As a result, faces with lower interfacial tension become more prominent in the final crystal shape.

The difference in growth rates of the various crystal faces, driven by their interfacial tensions, determines the crystal habit. Further, higher interfacial tension leads to a higher energy barrier for crystal face growth, slowing down the growth rate of that face.

Electrostatic repulsion between surface charges decreases interfacial tension in the solid-gas and liquid-gas interfaces, producing elongated solid or liquid particles during vapor condensation. Adsorbed molecules and ions that change interfacial tension can also change crystal habits. Temperature and supersaturation levels affect the interfacial tension and thus the growth rates of different crystal faces.

Higher temperatures can reduce the interfacial tension, generally increasing the growth rate but potentially affecting different faces differently based on their inherent properties.

Varying supersaturation levels can also influence which faces grow faster, altering the habit. This is represented in charts that show the ice crystal habits obtained under different conditions. Controlling crystal habits is used in the production of pharmaceuticals and materials. In mineralogy, it contributes to understanding the crystal formation conditions analogous to ice.

III. COULOMBIC EXPLOSION AND MATERIAL EJECTION

High surface charge density in water-air interfaces produces negative interfacial tension. Then, water fragmentation occurs without any further mechanical action, as seen in Fig. 3. It is known as the Coulombic explosion. Indeed, the explosion is observed when the electrostatic potential on insulators or poor conductors reaches some tens of kilovolts.

Fig. 3 Successive frames from a video capture a water drop sitting atop a biased steel needle. As the potential increases, the drop elongates and eventually emits water jets, visible as faint streaks in some frames. This demonstrates that Coulomb repulsion at the drop's surface reduces its surface tension [8, 11].

Measuring the speed and levitation data from charged ice crystals in an electric field yields surface charge density in the $0.62\text{--}1.25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ C}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ range, corresponding to $73\text{--}147 \text{ kV}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ electric fields, thus reaching the range measured within thunderstorms [22].

Figure 4 illustrates the effect of increasing voltage on the ejection of activated charcoal from an aluminum surface. As the voltage is incrementally increased from 0 to +5000V, the activated charcoal particles are observed to be ejected towards the grounded upper aluminum plate, demonstrating the influence of electrostatic forces.

Fig. 4 Sequence of five frames from a video showing the effect of increasing voltage (0, +1000V, +2000V, +4000V, and +5000V) applied to an aluminum surface with activated charcoal. As the potential increases, the activated charcoal is visibly ejected from the lower plate towards the grounded upper aluminum plate.

IV. PERSPECTIVES

Direct observation reveals that atmospheric clouds produce and store significant amounts of electrical energy, using air and water vapor as the primary inputs, but under gradients of temperature, pressure, and water vapor concentration. Understanding this has been an enormous challenge for researchers involved with atmospheric phenomena and environmental sciences in general. On the other hand, it reveals new possibilities for energy production and storage that have inspired inventors and the public but are still untapped.

Atmospheric physicists largely support a mechanism of excess charge formation in clouds based on ice crystal collision and fragmentation [23], driven by strong wind and the powerful turbulence in thunderclouds. This is consistent with water vapor condensation when cold air meets warmer, moist air, forming crystals of various sizes that move downwards under gravity, colliding when faster particles (due to larger size) collide with smaller particles. Crystal collisions are also provoked by the powerful wind created by the temperature and pressure gradients. Thus, cloud charge resides in ice crystals that tend to separate according to their sizes. This is represented in the dipolar or tripolar models of the electric structure of clouds.

The prevalent picture of charge separation and storage in clouds obeys the idea that macroscopic systems are electroneutral, often stated as the “electroneutrality principle.” It is supported by empirical observation of charge separation during mechanical operations, like milling, polishing, and abrasion or friction, like the often-mentioned Thales experiment that is often considered the discovery of electricity.

Independent of the present views, the accumulated recent knowledge on spontaneous water electrification contributes to an alternative mechanism for the electrification of the atmosphere and lightning formation.

The new results and ideas presented in the previous section II contribute new answers to essential questions on atmospheric electricity production, storage, and dissipation.

The first question is: how can large-scale charge separation occur in the atmosphere? This is answered by the results showing that interfaces are always electrified, and water is especially prone to electrification due to water ion partition. We know that the atmosphere exchanges charge with conductor and insulator solids and liquids, which is easily explained considering the possibilities for water ion partition in any interface. Thus, any aerosols or water droplets are the sites of charge separation and are large collections of miniature capacitors. We do not yet have detailed data on charge distribution in aerosols, the charge densities in different particles, and the distribution of water molecules or cluster ions in the atmosphere that permeates the particles. Still, we know that aerosols made by ultrasonic mechanical action contain positive and negative particles. The correlation between particle charge and size is known for aerosol produced in waterfalls or by air bubbling in pure water.

Thus, the participation of other factors like cosmic rays ionizing air molecules well beneath the ionosphere is not

essential to the electrification of the atmosphere. Water suffices.

Another question is: how can we understand the metastability implicit in atmospheric water supersaturation and the catastrophic (as in Catastrophe Theory) nature of lightning formation? Metastability in phase transitions is due to the interfacial tension between the initial and final phases, which creates an energy barrier. Electrification reduces surface tension and the energy barrier, eliminating or lowering the energy barrier. Increasing the electric potential in the supersaturated water vapor, the rate of condensation increases producing electrified droplets or crystals that further increase the electric potential. Thus, positive feedback produces an autocatalytic acceleration rate that increases the local energy density until a burst of energy dissipates it.

A third question refers to the chemical activity triggered by lightning. It is well known that nitrogen oxides are formed, contributing to soil fertilization. Is it only due to plasma formation during lightning, or are there other processes? The answer is that the chemical activity associated with the electrification of the atmosphere initiates much before lightning sets on. Any peaceful and cotton wool-like cumulus is an aqueous aerosol that we now know is an active microreactor delivering hydrogen peroxide and other chemicals, depending on the composition of the surrounding atmosphere. Thus, the chemical activity of self-electrified aerosol adds to that of atmospheric ozone, with a strong potential to deliver also many other chemicals that have not yet been detected or searched for.

V. CONCLUSION

Acknowledging that interfaces are always self-electrified and that atmospheric aerosols contain myriad interfaces produces a new vision of atmospheric electricity, including lightning formation and discharge.

Most importantly, this knowledge may generate new environmental technologies for controlling thunderstorms and suppressing their adverse conditions. Beyond that, new technologies for mitigating atmospheric pollution are also conceivable.

The potential for the exploration of aerosols and other common self-electrified interfaces for environmental remediation and chemical production is also enormous.

The published results now appear in hundreds of papers in the literature in different scientific areas. Criticism of the results has been eliminated, in the few cases when it appeared. Thus, there is room for much new science and technology based on the self-electrification of interfaces and the charge mosaics thus formed.

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